

ABOUT KARAKALPAK NATIONAL PATTERNS.

Yusupov Alimjon Turabayevich

Kamalova Feruza Yusupbaevna

Karakalpak state university, named after Berdak

Annotation: One of the Karakalpak national traditions are patterns, which we can fear that they are now depicted in modern multi-storey building styles, in objects used by people, in jewelry, in dresses with a unique combination of colors.

Keyword: decoration, patterns, stylizing elements in bird, hyacinth, plants, house, household items, geometric and others.

In the recent past, the most developed technologies of the Uzbek applied decorative art are the unique execution of such types as embroidery, ganchkery, wood carving, stone and bone carving, candlelight, knifemaking, jewelry, embroidery, Zoroastrianism, carpet weaving, embroidery, basketry, national names, their specific terms, the services of these art-specific schools, styles, as well as masters who have earned a name in these fields have gone all over the world.

The pattern is an Arabic image, a symbol of a flower, it is a Decoration That is characteristic of the repetition of bird, animal, plant world, geometric and other various forms in a certain order. As for the appearance of blackcurrant patterns in ancient times, our mothers embroidered felt with floral prints on dry fur, all kinds of ornaments were misty on the snowflakes. Later, these patterns were perfected by applying strength to wood pottery. In Karakalpak national patterns, mainly geometric shapes are used cuprer. The use of such forms is enslaved in the exterior and interior decoration of buildings. Warm colors are more often used in the decoration of the decoration of the painting of patterns, since the Spruce floor consists of cupier chul zones.

In Karakalpak national patterns, we can also use iymages, qarşins, esikqas, muyiz, earring, plant, baqa, iyt taban, quo'irshaq patterns. In this, the harmony of

warm, cold colors, the characteristic appearance of forms, the expression of nationality fall into the singular eye.

Esikqas.

Qarşins. Images.

It is also worth noting that these patterns can be found in various household items: carpets, kitchen items: trays, bowls, bowls, men's and women's dresses: in collar parts, pockets, embossed women's cases from the colors of dresses, which, for example, can be known as unmarried girls, young bridesmen, older women, cases such as azador women. The Karakalpak national blue jacket, on the other hand, was the girls ' wedding dress. We can see that our ancestors were used in the external decoration of the hearths that have come down to us.

Nowadays, we can also see our city in a different way, in the style of our modern multi-storey residential and communal buildings, in painting and carving methods, in interior decoration, walls and pathos, in landscapes, growing flowers and shrubs like patterns, in burschatkas, picking according to their color.

Bibliography:

1. E.I.Ruziyev. educational guide "geometric and Projective Drawing" Tashkent-2010
2. K.D.Rakhimov, A.S. Uralov textbook "design of objects of Landscape Architecture".
Publishing house " Sano-standard": Tashkent-2015
3. Sh.Kalliklishov, M.Amanbaev "Karakalpak national patterns" 2011
4. <https://meros.uz>, <https://mHYPERLINK> <https://mfa.uz> / " faHYPERLINK
<https://mfa.uz/.uz>